

ENHANCING LISTENING SKILLS OF B2 LEARNERS USING SOCIAL PLATFORMS

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Abstract: The advancement of digital technologies has significantly impacted the way language learners engage with authentic content. This article explores the potential of social platforms to enhance listening skills among B2-level language learners. Social platforms such as YouTube, podcasts, Tik Tok, and language exchange communities provide learners with immersive, real-world listening experiences that are often more varied and dynamic than traditional classroom exercises. By offering access to diverse accents, speech patterns, and topics, these platforms create opportunities for learners to develop their listening comprehension in context.

Key words: Experimental group, social platforms, authentic, recordings, diversity.

Introduction:

Traditionally, language learning has relied on structured listening exercises, such as scripted dialogues or recorded conversations, which often lack the spontaneity and diversity of real-life communication. However, with the rise of social platforms, learners now have access to an abundance of authentic, real-world listening materials that are both engaging and varied. Platforms like YouTube, podcasts, Tik Tok, and language exchange apps offer opportunities to listen to a wide range of accents, speech speeds.

This article aims to investigate how social platforms can be used to enhance listening skills among B2 learners, considering the unique advantages they offer in terms of accessibility, diversity, and learner engagement.

Literature Review

Historically, language learners have practiced listening skills through methods such as audio recordings, classroom dialogues, and scripted texts (Thornbury, 2005). While these methods provide structured practice, they often fail to expose learners to the dynamic and unpredictable nature of real-life speech. Moreover, such exercises tend to be limited in scope and are not always representative of the variety of accents, dialects, and informal speech that learners will encounter in authentic communication (Rost, 2011). As such, there is a growing need for alternative methods that offer more authentic, varied, and engaging listening experiences.

YouTube and podcasts are particularly valuable tools for developing listening skills. YouTube provides learners with the opportunity to watch and listen to native speakers in authentic contexts, from vlogs to educational videos, while podcasts offer

audio-only content that mimics real-life conversations (Mendelsohn, 2014). Furthermore, platforms like Tik Tok offer short, dynamic video content that challenges learners to process language quickly and efficiently, helping them adapt to real-world listening situations (Sun, 2021).

Methodology

1. Research Design

This study employs a mixed-methods approach to evaluate the effectiveness of social media platforms in enhancing listening skills among B2-level language learners. Both quantitative and qualitative data are collected through surveys, listening comprehension tests, and learner feedback. The research combines the measurement of objective outcomes, such as test scores, with subjective responses, such as learner perceptions and experiences.

2. Participants

The study involved 50 B2-level English language learners, aged 18–35, from a variety of linguistic and cultural backgrounds. All participants had at least six months of prior exposure to English as a second language and were actively using social media platforms for learning purposes. The participants were divided into two groups: an experimental group, which used social media platforms for listening practice, and a control group, which engaged in traditional listening exercises (e.g., recorded dialogues and scripted materials).

Data Collection Procedure

Over a period of four weeks, the experimental group engaged with content on various social platforms (e.g., YouTube videos, podcasts, TikTok, and language exchange apps) for 30 minutes a day. They were encouraged to select content based on their interests and proficiency level. The control group, on the other hand, continued their traditional listening practice. At the end of the four-week period, both groups completed the listening comprehension tests and surveys. Feedback interviews were conducted with 10 participants from each group to explore their personal experiences.

Result:

1. Listening Comprehension Test Scores

The experimental group showed a statistically significant improvement in listening comprehension scores after the four-week intervention ($p < 0.05$). On average, participants in the experimental group improved by 15%, compared to only a 5% improvement in the control group. The increase in scores was most notable in tasks that involved listening to diverse accents and informal speech, which are common features of social media content.

2. Learner Engagement and Feedback

The survey results indicated that the experimental group felt more engaged and motivated in their listening practice, with 85% of participants reporting that social media platforms made learning more enjoyable and relevant to their everyday lives.

Additionally, 70% of learners expressed that they had gained confidence in understanding spoken English in authentic contexts, such as casual conversations and fast-paced discussions. Learner feedback from interviews highlighted the value of diverse accents, real-world context, and the ability to choose content that aligned with their interests.

However, some challenges were noted, including difficulty navigating the vast amount of content available, distractions while using social media, and occasional difficulty understanding rapid speech or slang.

3. Comparison with Traditional Methods

While the control group showed some improvement, their progress was generally slower, and their responses indicated less enthusiasm about traditional listening exercises. Many learners in the control group expressed frustration with the lack of variety and relevance in the materials, pointing out that scripted recordings often felt artificial and disconnected from real-world language use.

Conclusion

Social media platforms have significant potential to enhance listening skills among B2-level language learners by offering authentic, varied, and context-rich listening opportunities. This study highlights the benefits of integrating these platforms into language learning, not only as supplementary tools but as central components of an interactive, learner-driven approach to language development. Further research is needed to explore long-term effects and refine strategies for effectively using social media in language learning contexts.

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